

Acoustical and Flow Behaviour Analysis of Various Muffler Designs through CFD Analysis

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Abstract: Mufflers are installed within the exhaust system of most internal combustion engines, although the muffler is not designed to serve any primary exhaust function. The muffler is engineered as an acoustic soundproofing device designed to reduce the loudness of the sound pressure created by the engine by way of acoustic quieting. Pressure contour and Velocity contours have been obtained for the Five muffler models using CFD analysis. Acoustic Power levels, Transmission losses are also determined for each of the five models. As Shown by results, we can observe Model number one i.e. Muffler design with no extended inlet and outlet pipes inside the chamber has the least Acoustic power level of 45.32 dB. But for Model number one the Transmission loss is at low rate (3.72) as a result the efficiency of the muffler will be poor. For Model number four i.e. Three chambered muffler (with inlet and outlet pipe ends closed) the Transmission loss is at a high rate (9.92) as a result the efficiency will be great for this model but for Model number four the Sound emission is at a large rate 70.9dB which is not preferable. Taking the considerations of back pressure, as back pressure in Model number three is less. Model number three is the best optimum muffler model with an acoustic power level of 51.08 dB.

Keywords: Mufflers, Exhaust System, Internal Combustion Engines, Pressure contour, Velocity contours, CFD analysis, Acoustic Power levels, Transmission losses

I. Introduction

One area of mechanical engineering is automobile engineering. It covers the different kinds of autos, their gearbox systems, and their uses. The various kinds of vehicles used to carry people, products, etc. are called automobiles. In essence, internal combustion processes are the basis for all vehicle kinds. To start the gearbox moving in cars, various fuels are burned inside the cylinder at a greater temperature. As a result, every mechanical and automotive engineer must to be familiar with the many applications and mechanisms of automobiles.

The exhaust system directs engine exhaust gases to the back of the vehicle body and reduces noise generated during engine operation. Track the movement of exhaust gases from the tailpipe to the engine exhaust manifold. Find out what the parts are called. To lessen the quantity of harmful (poisonous) materials that an engine produces, different emission control techniques are employed. Certain systems stop fuel vapors from getting into the atmosphere, which is the air that surrounds the earth. Unburned and partially burnt fuel are eliminated from the engine exhaust by other emission control devices.

Millions of cars contribute to the total emissions. These pollutants are byproducts of fuel evaporation and engine combustion processes. Despite the fact that the number of vehicles on the road is constantly increasing, research indicates that between 10 and 30 percent of them are the primary source of air pollution.

Toxic emissions from the combustion of gases, usually from automobile engines, are carried out by a mixture of metallic pipes in a conventional exhaust system. In essence, a vehicle's safe and dependable operation depends on its exhaust system operating efficiently. Before releasing the gases into the atmosphere, the most recent exhaust systems are made to clean them. Engine efficiency is improved with modified

systems that allow for a smoother gas flow.

Back pressure develops when there is any obstruction in the engine's exhaust gas passage to the atmosphere, which lowers the engine's efficiency and, consequently, power. In order to reduce back pressure, performance-oriented mufflers and exhaust systems use a variety of technologies and techniques to reduce noise. However, the general adage that more power equals more noise applies to most of these systems.

There are numerous exhaust systems of this type that employ different designs and construction techniques: Vector mufflers use slanted baffles to cancel out exhaust impulses, or they use a lot of concentric cones for larger diesel trucks or performance cars.

Marshall and Milton Reeves received a patent for the first silencer in 1897. The primary part of the exhaust system for reducing acoustic exhaust noises is the silencer. Today's market offers a wide variety of muffler styles. Some are straight through glass packs, glass packs, chambered, and combinations of those. It is intended to lessen the acoustic sound pressures produced by combustion. The most popular material found within conventional mufflers is fiberglass. To help with absorption and lessen undesirable exhaust sounds, additional materials could be wool, fibre mats, rock minerals, or basic metal chambers.

A silencer needs to be resilient enough to endure the conditions under which a car runs. This includes the frequencies of engine noise, dangerous off-road driving situations and the fact that the majority of the silencer needs to resist corrosion and rust.

II. CFD Analysis

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is a branch of fluid mechanics that uses numerical analysis and data structures to analyze and solve problems that involve fluid flows. Computers are used to perform the calculations required to simulate the free-stream flow of the fluid, and the interaction

of the fluid (liquids and gases) with surfaces defined by boundary conditions.

CFD is based on the Navier-Stokes equations. Arising from applying Newton's second law to fluid motion, together with the assumption that the stress in the fluid is the sum of a diffusing viscous term and a pressure term, these equations describe how the velocity, pressure, temperature, and density of a moving fluid are correlated.

Ongoing research yields software that improves the accuracy and speed of complex simulation scenarios such as transonic or turbulent flows. Initial validation of such software is typically performed using experimental apparatus as wind tunnels. In addition, previously performed analytical or empirical analysis of a particular problem can be used for comparison. A final validation is often performed using full scale testing, such as flight tests.

III. Advantages of CFD

- Gain insight into systems that might be difficult to test through experimentation.
- Foresee performance and optimize the design accordingly. Without modifying or installing real systems, CFD simulation can forecast which changes in design are most vital for improving performance.
- Predict mass flow rates, pressure drops, heat transfer rates, and fluid dynamic forces such as lift, drag and pitching moments.
- Lower costs by using CFD simulations instead of physical experimentation to retrieve essential engineering data.
- Introduce engineering data early in the design process. Simulations can be executed in a far shorter period of time when compared to physical testing.
- Simulate real conditions. Some flow and heat transfer processes cannot be physically tested, e.g. hypersonic flow. But CFD provides the ability to theoretically simulate any physical condition.
- Simulate ideal conditions. CFD permits great control over the physical processes, and offers the ability to isolate specific phenomena for study.

IV. Methodology

Methodology for the current research comprises of following steps-

- First of all, previous research studies are to be studied so as to confine the area of research and the confined area is to analyze the performance of an exhaust system through improvement of backpressure along with material and shape optimization of muffler used in it.
- Second step is to develop the 3D model of exhaust system.
- Next step would be to develop the 3D models of several mufflers having different shapes.

- Now each muffler would be fitted with exhaust system and CFD analysis for Heat transfer across the exhaust system would be conducted.
- Comparative analysis is to be performed in order to evaluate and determine the best suitable muffler.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the Methodology Used for Current Research

V. Data Analysis & Interpretation

A. Model With No Perforations and With No Extended Inlet and Outlet Pipes

Fig. 2 Total Pressure Contour for M1

Fig. 3 Velocity Contour for M1

From the fig. 5.2, it can be observed that the pressure is decreasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet pressure is 103.24 Pa and Outlet pressure is 67.31 Pa. From the fig. 5.3, it can be observed that the velocity is increasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet velocity is 10.78 m/s and Outlet velocity is 13.82 m/s.

B. Model With Perforations (Inlet and Outlet Pipe Ends Closed)

Fig. 4 Total Pressure Contour for M2

Fig. 5 Velocity Contour for M2

From the fig. 5.4, it can be observed that the pressure is decreasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet pressure is 156.37 Pa and Outlet pressure is 61.47 Pa. From the fig. 5.5, it can be observed that the velocity is increasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet velocity is 10.78 m/s and Outlet velocity is 13.52 m/s.

C. Model With Perforations (Inlet and Outlet Pipe Ends Opened)

Fig. 6 Total Pressure Contour for M3

Fig. 7 Velocity Contour for M3

From the fig. 5.6, it can be observed that the pressure is decreasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet pressure is 70.27 Pa and Outlet pressure is 69.26 Pa. From the fig. 5.7, it can be observed that the velocity is increasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet velocity is 10.78 m/s and Outlet velocity is 14.17 m/s.

D. Three Chambered Model with Perforations (Inlet and Outlet Pipe Ends Closed)

Fig. 8 Total Pressure Contour for M4

Fig. 9 Velocity Contour for M4

From the fig. 5.8, it can be observed that the pressure is decreasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet pressure is 172.64 Pa and Outlet pressure is 55.11 Pa. From the fig. 5.9, it can be observed that the velocity is increasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet velocity is 10.78 m/s and Outlet velocity is 12.78 m/s.

E. Three Chambered Model with Perforations (Inlet and Outlet Pipe Ends Opened)

Fig. 10 Total Pressure Contour for M5

Fig. 11 Velocity Contour for M5

From the fig. 5.10, it can be observed that the pressure is decreasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet pressure is 147.11 Pa and Outlet pressure is 56.51 Pa. From the fig. 5.11, it can be observed that the velocity is increasing from inlet to Outlet. Inlet velocity is 10.78 m/s and Outlet velocity is 12.64 m/s.

VI. Result Discussion

Model no:	Acoustic Power Level (dB)	Pi (Pa)	Po (Pa)	$TL=20\log_{10}(P_i/P_o)$
Model 1	45.32	103.24	67.31	3.72
Model 2	66.27	156.37	61.47	8.11
Model 3	51.08	70.27	69.26	0.12
Model 4	70.9	172.64	55.11	9.92
Model 5	66.11	147.11	56.51	8.31

Table 1 CFD analysis results of each model

Pressure contour and Velocity contours have been obtained for the Five muffler models using CFD analysis. Acoustic Power levels, Transmission losses are also determined for each of the five models. As Shown in the table 5.2 we can observe Model 1 i.e. Muffler design with no extended inlet and outlet pipes inside the chamber has the least Acoustic power level of 45.32 dB

But for Model 1 the Transmission loss is at low rate (3.72) as a result the efficiency of the muffler will be poor. For Model 4 i.e. Three chambered muffler (with inlet and outlet pipe ends closed) the Transmission loss is at a high rate (9.92) as a result the efficiency will be great for this model but for Model 4 the Sound emission is at a large rate 70.9dB which is not preferable. Taking the considerations of back pressure, as back pressure in Model 3 is less. Model 3 is the best optimum muffler model with an acoustic power level of 51.08 dB.

VII. Conclusion

A numerical analysis is carried out on acoustical and flow behaviour analysis of various muffler designs and the following conclusions are made.

- The increase in restriction to the flow is found to increase the back pressure.
- From the various cases considered for best possible muffler designs, 3rd case is found to be a preferable choice at it is having least transmission losses.
- Acoustic power level comparison of different cases shown least APL value for 1st case. But this is not considered as suitable design because of high pressure drop and transmission loss.
- Greater the installation of baffle plates, greater the generation of back pressure.

- Pressure decreases from inlet pipe to outlet pipe.
- Velocity increases from inlet pipe to outlet pipe.
- As Exhaust gases from the exhaust manifold travel with a high velocity they tend to travel through larger openings in the muffler.

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